
DESIGN AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF A HIGH PERFORMANCE A-Fe₂O₃-X₂S (0001) BASED HETEROJUNCTION SOLAR CELLS WITH ZNS ETL AND CUI HTL USING SCAPS-1D

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ABSTRACT

With several years of research on solar cell development, the energy conversion efficiency has seen a great improvement but it is still a big problem to design an eco-friendly cost-effective solar cell with high conversion efficiency. For eco-friendly earth-abundant solar cell fabrication, Sulphur-doped α -Fe₂O₃(0001) has offered a very promising absorber material. But defect-free fabrication is one of the most possible challenges during α -Fe₂O₃-xS_x (0001)-based solar cell fabrication. The purpose of this research is to use the earth-abundant (Sulphur-doped) α -Fe₂O₃-xS_x (0001) material as a solar absorber and to see how the efficiency of the newly proposed ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O₃-xS_x(0001)/CuI structure is affected by CuI as an HTL material and ZnS as an ETL material. Besides, Cu, Au, Ni are used as a back metal contact and Mo as a front-contact material to see their impact on solar cell performances.

In this research work, we simulate the photovoltaic (PV) efficiency using SCAPS-1D software. During the simulation process, we implanted defect densities (Nt) to each layer as well as the interface between the absorber layer and other adjacent layers. CuI HTL and ZnS ETL were found to play a promising role in minimizing non-radiative recombination at the interfaces by establishing a more auspicious band alignment with the absorber substrate. The value of layer parameters (such as thickness, NA, ND, Nt), Operating temperature, metalwork function of back-contact, etc. is varied with a decent range to find out the optimum PV performance of the proposed structure. From the simulation study of the proposed cell using the SCAPS-1D simulator, it was discovered that a lower acceptor concentration (NA) and comparatively thicker absorber layer performed better. For better results, a thick HTL layer and a very thin ETL layer with a high carrier concentration are also needed.

In this work, the simulated conversion efficiency (η) 18% to 37.2378% was obtained in the case of best suited Ni as back contact metal depending on the absorber defect. CuI and ZnS are required to become HTL and ETL, respectively, with the possible lowest absorber defect, for fabricating low-cost, high-efficiency, and non-toxic sulfur-doped α -Fe₂O₃-xS_x (0001)-based heterojunction solar cells, according to the findings of this report.

Keywords: A-Fe₂O₃-X₂S (0001), Cui, Zns, Efficiency, SCAPS-1D.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy describes the ability to do work and is a must needed for life processes. It can take many different types, including kinetic, thermal, potential, electrical, chemical, nuclear, and so on. Human energy consumption requirements have grown steadily with time throughout human history. Early humans had decent energy demands, most importantly food and fuel for fires to cook food and keep them warm. In the present society, we consume a hundred times as much energy per person as early humans.

Most of the energy we use today directly comes from fossil fuels. But fossil fuels have a great disadvantage because of their finite amount on a human time scale as well as non-renewable behavior and have negative impacts on the atmosphere at the same time. But in renewable energy, all materials serve as everlasting energy sources. The primary sources of renewable energy are tides, geothermal, hydroelectricity, wind, and sunlight. Although the amount of energy derived from these supplies is smaller than that derived from non-renewable sources, the concept of using an everlasting supply of energy has gained a lot of interest. Over the years, researchers, experts, and business class industries have worked together to find a solution to the ever-increasing energy demand. The sum of solar radiated power that reaches the planet is enormous and one hour of solar irradiation equals the amount of energy that humanity consumes annually [1].

At present, the use of sunlight for the generation of clean and green energy has received tremendous attention because of the gradual exhaustion of natural resources of energy and the deterioration of the environment. Renewable energy ensures a steady stream of electricity and diversifies carbon sources, which improves energy protection and reduces the chance of fuel drops while lowering the demand for non-renewable energy with limited resources. So, it is important to utilize solar energy by developing solar energy conversion efficiency to meet current and potential global energy demands at the terawatt (TW) scale. Solar cells, among other possible technologies for outright transforming sunlight into useful energy without causing any negative consequences, are prominent in this course.

Solar cells are optoelectronic devices that can turn direct sunlight, as well as an artificial or atmospheric light, into a usable source of electricity. The primary goal of researchers in this field is to create photovoltaic devices that are earth-friendly, non-toxic, low-cost, and highly effective. In the most commonly used crystalline Si (c-Si) based solar cells, the maximum cell efficiency obtained is up to 24.5 percent from solar module [2] and Kaneka Corporation designed the best Si-solar cell, which delivers a conversion efficiency of 26.7 percent from single-cell [3&4] among the technologies based on the wafer. For c-Si solar cells, the highest theoretical PCE obtained was 31% [5].

Because of the many shortcomings of the aforementioned c-Si solar cell (such as weight, inflexibility, the expense of Si wafer, and costly processing technology) in recent decades, finding the suitable low-cost stuff to fabricate solar devices is the key topic for research on solar cells.

Thin-film solar cells (TFSCs) are becoming eminent as a result of their higher stability on performance at existing operating temperature and tunable direct bandgap energies. Another interesting point of choosing TFSCs over the solar cells made of c-Si is the lower consumption of construction ingredients. The first published thin-film single-junction Cu₂S/CdS solar cell provides around 9.1% PCE. However, owing to copper diffusion into the CdS matrix and CdS layer doping, long-term efficiency was deteriorating and further study on Cu₂S/CdS devices was halted [6-7]. Among the TFSCs, researchers prefer amorphous silicon (a-Si)-based cells because of available substrate supply, low processing temperature, non-toxic behavior, and cost-efficient technologies for processing. Amorphous-Si-based TFSCs have a conversion efficiency of up to 13.6 percent [8].

In recent years, as an earth-abundant and low-cost TFSCs, chalcogenide-based solar cells have made significant contributions. With PCEs of 22.1%, solar cells made of cadmium telluride (CdTe) are the most common second-generation TFSCs [4]. But, in CdTe-based TFSCs, Cd is known to be a dangerous substance for the atmosphere, and Te is a poisonous as well as rare earth element [9]. The first reported heterojunction CuInSe₂ (CIS)/CdS photovoltaic TFSCs by Wagner et al. in 1974 [10] turned the interest of the researchers on CIS TFSCs after reporting the promising 9.4% efficient CIS cell in 1981 [11]. At the laboratory level, the CIGS solar cell is more productive among the TFSCs family because it offers a tunable bandgap (1to1.7eV range) and expected (~10⁵ cm⁻¹) optical absorption coefficient [12]. Nakamura et al. fabricate the 23.35% efficient champion CIGS-based solar cell [13]. But, CIGS technology has also many drawbacks in terms of overall viability [14–16] and high stuff costs arising from the strong demand for In from the show industry due to the use of infrequent Ga & In components [17]. Due to being eco-friendly, earth-abundant, cost-effective, and highly efficient, the kesterite-based CZTS and the compounds related to CZTS (such as CZTSe and CZTSSe) are alternative materials to be considered as solar absorbers for TFSCs [18-21]. As an absorber, CZTS was first discovered in 1988 [18]. The report revealed that the efficiency has risen of CZTS/CZTSe based TFSCs from 0.66% in 1997 [22] to 12.6% in 2013 [23-24]. After mixing silver with CZTS (ACZTS), the designed (CdS/ ACZTS/CZTS/ITO) structure provides

maximum of 17.59% efficiency [25]. Because of its defect-prone system, while preparing CZTS like compounds, lots of defects remained in the structure. As a result, CIGS and CdTe-based cells are still more efficient than these promising CZTS/CZTSe components. Multi-junction solar cells with five junctions (GAIInAs/GAIInP/GaAs/AlGaInAs/AlGaInP) tandem geometry have achieved the maximum PCE of 38.8% due to multiple absorber layers for collecting light from different parts of the solar spectrum. However, the high manufacturing cost of these solar cells poses a significant obstacle for the PV industry [26].

TFSCs suffer from a poor performance such as a-Si, poisonous ingredients such as Cd in CdTe, a scarcity of natural resources such as Te in CdTe and In and Ga in CIGS-based structure, and high production cost of the multi-junction structure. From the viewpoint of commercialization, solar cells that are a bit less efficient but long-lasting and low-cost will prove to be a successful commercial alternative. Being naturally abundant, non-toxic, environmentally friendly, stable, and having a favorable bandgap ($\sim 2.1\text{eV}$) [27] $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ is an attractive material in solar energy conversion applications. The bandgap of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ decreases promisingly with increasing sulfur doping concentration and most interestingly, unlike pure $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, the p-type $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ with $x\approx 0.17$ (around 5.6% concentration of sulfur) shows a direct bandgap of $\sim 1.45\text{eV}$, as well as the absorption coefficient, is $\sim 105\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [27-28] and lower carrier effective masses (The effective masses of electron and hole are $1.3m_e$ and $1.6m_e$) [27]. These properties explicitly suggest that it may be a viable material for low-cost solar cell chip fabrication with the right sulfur doping concentration. W. Bergermayer et al. have technically demonstrated the electronic composition of the pure hematite $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ surface [29]. J. An et al. investigated a film model of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ with (0001) surface, as well as S adsorption on the film's surface and isovalent S doping, using the DFT+U process [28].

We suggest that for $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ -based thin-film solar cells, an n-type ZnS layer be used as a buffer layer. Because of its proper band alignment with $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$, It has the potential to be a useful electron transport layer (ETL) for $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ -based solar cells. Copper iodide (CuI) has been investigated as an HTL layer because of its capability to capture holes more effectively and reduce electron-hole recombination in the space charge region.

The SCAPS-1D program is used to model the solar cell's basic (ITO/ZnS/ $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ /CuI) configuration in order to analyze and refine the device's different PV output parameters. Cu, Au, Ir, Ni, W are suitable back contact metals for this structure. Copper (Cu) (100), Gold (Au) (111), Nickel (Ni) (111) were used as back contact materials in this study, while Molybdenum (Mo) (114) is used as front contact material [30]. To achieve the best cell efficiency, the thickness, carrier concentration, working temperatures, the back-contact metal work function, and defect density of different layers were all varied.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Solar cell structure:

The most popular TFSCs consist of semiconductor buffer layers surrounding the absorber layer. The heart of a solar cell is the absorber layer, which absorbs photons from light sources and converts them to electrons and holes in the conduction and valance bands. One of the two buffer layer is incorporated to allow photo-generated electrons (PGEs) to flow freely to an adjacent electrode while preventing the ingoing photo-generated holes (PGHs) from that electrode. PGHs are sent into the other buffer layer, which is on the opposite side of the absorber membrane, while PGEs are blocked from entering the other electrode. Buffer layers are considered to be wide band gap, so that a very few of the incident photons may absorb within them.

Before building a system structure, the band diagram is important. On the basis of different parameters, the optimal ETL, HTL, and contact-metal for this structure is considered. For $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ -based solar cells, a planar heterojunction structure was used with layer configurations of Mo/ITO/ZnS/ $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ /CuI/(Cu or Au or Ni) as depicted in Figure 1(a). In this study, we use three back-contact metals, Cu, Au, and Ni in the structure one by one and compare their performances to find the best cell structure. Here, ITO is used as a window layer, whereas as an ETL, Absorber and HTL layer we incorporate ZnS, $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$, and CuI respectively. Figure 1(b) depicts a band diagram obtained from the simulation of the proposed cell structure. The $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-xSx}(0001)$ /CuI interface has a valence band energy difference of $+0.14\text{ eV}$ and conduction band offset (CBO) between them is $+1.79\text{ eV}$. It is crucial in order to avoid the carrier recombination in the absorber

layer as well as allow the hole to flow through the HTL to the back-contact. The conduction band offset (CBO) is +0.01eV at the ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001) interface, Which is decent for the photoexcited electrons to easily flow to the front electrode. The valence band energy of the α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001) absorber layer is much lower (~2.24 eV) than the ZnS ETL layer which refuse to allow the entrance of photogenerated holes into ETL.

Figure 1(a). Schematic structure of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)-based heterojunction solar cell.

Figure 1(b). Energy band diagram of the Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)/CuI/Ni heterojunction solar cell.

2.2 Numerical modeling and simulation parameters:

The SCAPS-1D (solar cell capacitance simulator) software was engaged in this work to simulate a normal solar cell with the Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)/CuI/(Cu or Au or Ni) structure. SCAPS-1D is an important one-dimensional simulation program in the research community that solves three basic semiconductor transport equations (such as, (a) Continuity equations for free holes, (b) Continuity equations for free electrons and (c) Poisson’s equation) under steady state condition [31]. SCAPS mathematically addresses these three coupled fractional differential equations for the electrostatic potential (carrier concentration) as a function of position x. During designing solar cell with SCAPS-1D, we can stack up to seven layers, defining all related material properties as grading profiles. At the same time, we may introduce multiple defects, and much more, significantly increasing the applicability over the analytical solution. It was exercised in this study to design the proper cell structure and investigate the efficiency of Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)/CuI/(Au or Cu or Ni) solar cell with optimized material parameters. Deep bulk stage and interface defect recombination can be used in the program (non-radiative recombination). Shockley-Read-Hall recombination compensates for direct band-to-band recombination (i.e., radiative recombination) and device recombination, are two forms of recombination losses that occur in the system under consideration (propagated by defects or traps).

Table 1: Simulation Parameters of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)-based Structure [28, 32-38].

Parameters	ITO	ETL(ZnS)	Absorber α -Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)	HTL(CuI)
Thickness (μ m)	0.02	0.03	0.2-2.0	0.50-2.30

Bandgap E_g (eV)	3.50 [33]	3.68 [34]	1.45 [32]	3.10 [36]
Electron Affinity, χ (eV)	4.60	3.90	3.89	2.10
Dielectric permittivity (relative) ϵ_r	8.90	8.30	14	6.5
Effective CB density, N_c (cm ⁻³)	2.2×10^{18}	6.35×10^{18}	3.71×10^{19}	2.8×10^{19}
Effective VB density, N_v (cm ⁻³)	1.8×10^{19}	6.03×10^{19}	5.067×10^{19}	1.0×10^{19}
Thermal velocity of electron (cms ⁻¹)	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}
Thermal velocity of hole (cms ⁻¹)	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{17}
Electron mobility, μ_n (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10	250	4.7	100
Hole mobility, μ_p (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10	40	3.8	44
Donor density, N_D (cm ⁻³)	1.0×10^{21}	$10^{18} - 10^{21}$	0	0
Acceptor density, N_A (cm ⁻³)	0	0	$10^{12} - 10^{16}$	$10^{16} - 10^{20}$
Defect density, N_t (cm ⁻³)	1.0×10^{15}	1.0×10^{15}	$10^{13} - 10^{17}$	1.0×10^{15}

The material properties of the α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001) absorber layer were carefully chosen from legitimate literature, theory, and, in certain circumstances, plausible assumptions in order to represent the best possible outcome under real-world situations. Table 1 summarizes the parameters for each material used in this simulation. We measured conduction and valance bands effective density of states by using $N_c = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi m_e^* kT}{h^2} \right)^{3/2}$ and $N_v = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi m_h^* kT}{h^2} \right)^{3/2}$ [42] equations where, K = Boltzmann constant, T = temperature, h = Planck's constant and m_e^* and m_h^* denotes the respective electron and hole effective masses. In this work, we use $\mu_e = \frac{e\tau}{m_e^*}$ and $\mu_h = \frac{e\tau}{m_h^*}$ equations to calculate the respective electron and hole mobilities of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001) absorber layer. Where effective masses (electron and hole) are $m_e^* = 1.3me$ and $m_h^* = 1.6me$ for α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001) C. Xia *et al* [32] and τ define the time between collision which is calculated by using the value of carrier mobility μ taken from S. S. Shinde *et al.*[37] and band effective mass m_e^* of pure hematite α - Fe₂O₃ from J. Chem. Phys. 144, 164704 (2016) [38].

Table 2: Interface defect Parameters used in the simulation of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)-based Structure.

Parameters	ZnS/Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)	Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)/CuI
Defect type	Neutral	Neutral
Capture cross section of electrons (cm ²)	1×10^{-19}	1×10^{-19}
Capture cross section of holes (cm ²)	1×10^{-19}	1×10^{-19}
Energetic distribution	Single	Single
Energy level with regards to E_v (eV)	0.600	0.600
Total density (cm ⁻²)	1×10^{16}	1×10^{16}

Table 3: Employed simulation parameters for front and back contact.

Parameters	Back-contact electrical properties	Front-contact electrical properties
Surface recombination velocity of electrons (cms ⁻¹)	1.0×10^5	1.0×10^7
Surface recombination velocity of holes (cms ⁻¹)	1.0×10^7	1.0×10^5
Work function values (eV)	5.1; Cu (100) 5.31; Au (111)	4.5; Mo (114)

	5.35; Ni (111)	
Working temperature (K)	300	

Table 4: Parameters of PV performance for different back contact incorporated in the cell configuration.

Cell configuration	V _{oc} (volt)	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)/CuI/Cu	0.914387	32.20563422	74.7923	22.0252
Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)/CuI/Au	0.914599	45.12716735	79.3518	32.7511
Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe ₂ O _{3-x} S _x (0001)/CuI/Ni	0.915114	46.22611678	80.7007	34.1381

In each semiconductor layer, we have introduced a single form of deep-level defect. Aside from that, each arrangement contains two carrier recombination defect interfaces. The first was between ETL(ZnS) and Absorber (α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)), and the second was between Absorber (α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)) and HTL(CuI). The interfacial defect characteristics utilized in this study are summarized in Table 2. The total defect density was set to $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and the defect form was set to neutral, whereas the cross sections electron capture (cm^2) and cross section holes capture (cm^2) are fitted to $1 \times 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2$. Table 3 contains the parameters for the front contact, back contact, and operating temperatures. At the back contact, the reflection was considered to be 90%, and at the front contact, it was considered to be 10% [39]. Experimental absorption coefficient data of ITO, ZnS, α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001), and CuI were employed in the modeling from the literature [32, 38, 40–41]. In this work, the Solar cells are simulated with the incident light power 1000 W/m² at AM 1.5 G 1 sun spectrum, whereas the solar cell was illuminated through the ITO window layer side [43].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, we adopt the standard Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)/CuI/(Cu or Au or Ni) cell structure using SCAPS-1D simulator. Figure 2(a) represents the J-V characteristics curve of the cell.

Figure 2(a): J-V characteristics curve of Mo/ITO/ZnS/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x(0001)/CuI solar cell with three different back contact metal, **(b)** External quantum efficiency curve for different back metal contact.

From the J-V analysis depicted in figure 2(a), we can see that Ni contact instead of Cu or Au provide much better PV performance where metal work function of Copper, Gold, and Nickel are 5.10 eV, 5.31 eV and 5.35 eV respectively. That behavior indicates that, metal with high work function is needed for the designed solar to get better output performance. At the back contact/buffer layer interface, the minority carrier surface recombination is responsible for those characteristics, because it leads to enhance the dark current and reduce V_{oc} [44]. To enhance the output performance, it is very important to reduce the minority carrier surface recombination at the buffer layer/back contact interface. The obtained efficiency value for the use of Cu, Au and

Ni contact are, 22.03%, 32.75% and 34.14% respectively. This significant gain in efficiency is attributable to a jump in V_{OC} from 0.914387 mV to 0.915114 mV, a jump in FF from 74.7923 percent to 80.7007 percent, and a modest jump in J_{SC} from 32.20563422 mA/cm² to 46.22611678 mA/cm². As a result of the J-V study, the insertion of contact material with higher work function like Ni is advantageous and results in devices with improved electrical performance in terms of J_{SC} , FF and V_{OC} . The EQE spectra of the designed solar cell for all three back contact metal are shown in figure 2(b) in the wavelength rages from 300 nm to 900 nm. It is feasible to see the effect of the contact metal on the quantum efficiency of the designed cell by comparing the obtained EQE spectra. Particularly when the CuI layer is added in between absorber and back contact, the EQE improves significantly at longer wavelengths. This is owing to the CuI layer's effective creation of a back surface field, which collects photogenerated carriers effectively. Furthermore, CuI layer behind the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x(0001)$ layer can improve the reflection of light at near-infrared spectra.

3.1. The influence of the back contact metal work function on the PV performance of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x(0001)$ -based solar cells.

The material used for the solar cell's back-contact has a big impact on the efficiency of that device. A rather high metal work function is needful to introduce ohmic contact with the absorber layer or the HTL. As a front contact metal, we incorporate Molybdenum (Mo). To explore the impact of the metal's electron work function on the back contact on a systemic level, we experimented with work function values ranging from 4.5 eV to 5.7 eV in the simulation. A remarkable increase in solar cell performance was discovered by raising the back contact metal work function from 4.5 eV to 5.7 eV, as seen in the figure 3. Figure 3(a) describes that V_{OC} get saturated after the metal work function above 4.9 eV but the value of V_{OC} rapidly increases at the 4.5 eV to 4.9 eV range. Except V_{OC} curve, all of the Current Density, FF, and PCE curve show almost similar trends and increase swiftly when the work function value rises from 5.1 eV to 5.5 eV and these data suggest saturation behavior above the crucial metal work function (5.5 eV). With increasing the metal work function the majority charge carrier (hole) barrier height at the back contact interface falls by reducing the charge carrier interfacial recombination and thereby enhance the cell performance. Findings from the obtained graph unfold that a back contact metal having the work function value more than 5.3 eV is necessary to enhance the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x(0001)$ -based solar cell performance. To get a high-performance mark in this system, metals such as Au, Ir, Ni, and W can be employed as back metal contacts. In this work, we suggest to use Ni (111) metal as a back contact.

Figure 3(a-d): The effect of work function value of back contact metal on the PV performance parameters of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x(0001)$ -based solar cells.

3.2. The effect of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001) absorber layer properties (Thickness and Carrier concentration) on the PV performances of the device.

Manufacturing environmentally acceptable, cost-effective solar cells with high PCE and very thin absorber layers is the main challenge in the area of solar cells. Since it has a significant impact on photogenerated excitons and charge carrier extraction [33], it is an important option for solar cell structuring. As the absorber layer thickness rises, the longer wavelength of light can produce a significant quantity of electron-hole pairs. But the depletion layer grows extremely close to the back contact when the absorber layer thickness decreases, and more electrons are caught by the back contact for recombination [45]. As a result, a small number of electrons participate in the generation process, resulting in a lower fill factor and efficiency.

Figure 4(a-d): The effect of thickness of absorber layer on the PV performance parameters of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cells.

Figure 4 depicts the relationship between PV parameters and the thickness absorber layer as obtained from the simultaneous simulation. At the beginning, the ZnS ETL's carrier concentration and thicknesses were all adjusted to 10^{21} cm^{-3} and 30 nm, respectively. While the CuI HTL was tuned to 2.0 μm and 10^{19} cm^{-3} , respectively, for the same parameters. To optimize the device performance, $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001) absorber layer thickness was varied in the range of 0.2 μm to 2.0 μm . The figure 4(a) represents that there is decrease of V_{oc} from 0.93616 volt to 0.85297 volt while increasing the absorber thickness. The current density J_{sc} shows very small response with variation of absorber thickness, as seen in figure 4(b). To reach a higher fill factor, a good absorber is needed. As seen in figure 4(c), the fill factor of the cell falls by huge margin as the absorber layer thickness increases. Figure 4(d) suggests that, relatively thinner absorber is required for the designed solar cell to get better efficiency as the PCE decreases when we progress from thinner to thicker absorber because there is a trade-off between carrier extraction and light absorption. Device experiences less absorption when a thin layer is employed and thereby the photocurrent is reduced, but carrier extraction is increased. Because of the increased absorption with a thicker absorber layer, carrier production increases, but collection efficiency decreases owing to recombination, which affects V_{oc} [46]. As well as considering the reproducibility fact, we assumed 0.5 μm is the optimal absorber layer thickness.

Figure 5(a-d): The effect of Carrier Concentration of absorber layer on the PV performance parameters of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x (0001)-based solar cells.

Photovoltaic solar cells (PSCs) output can be improved by adding sufficient doping to the absorber layer because it generally influences the total carrier generation and recombination of the solar cell [33]. And at the same time, it plays crucial role on carrier transport property of the cell.

Figure 6: Total Recombination rate (a) at CuI/ α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x (0001) interface and (b) α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x (0001)/ZnS interface.

The efficiency of the device was investigated by changing the absorber doping concentration from 10¹² cm⁻³ to 10¹⁶ cm⁻³. Figure 5 depicts the relationship between PV parameters and absorber layer carrier concentration. The figure 5(a) and 5(c) represents that there is very small change in V_{oc} and FF with increasing doping concentration and show opposite trends. From figure 5(b) we can see that J_{sc} is almost constant at lower doping concentration but it falls rapidly when concentration increases above 10¹⁵ cm⁻³ and thereby PCE curve follow the similar trends of J_{sc} curve. This is due to the higher carrier recombination rate at higher doping concentration of absorber and Higher absorber carrier concentrations resulted in greater impurity scattering, which raised the absorber layer's resistivity and, as a result, lowered J_{sc} [33]. The overall carrier recombination rate at the interfaces of the various layers, as well as at the bulk layer, are depicted in Figure 6. At the interface,

band offset and defect density increases. As a result, total recombination increases, thereby increasing the resistivity of the absorber layer and lowering J_{sc} and the overall FF. Figure 6 (b) also shows that at higher hole concentrations ($>10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), carrier recombination become high within the ABS/ETL interface's space charge region (SCR). This indicates that increased non-radiative recombination within SCR of the ABS/ETL interface at higher hole concentrations may be another cause for the observed J_{sc} and PCE reduction [33]. Hence, we found the optimized absorber layers acceptor density is 10^{14} cm^{-3} . At $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ thickness and 10^{14} cm^{-3} carrier concentration of the absorber layer provide the optimum efficiency $>34\%$.

3.3. The effect of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001) absorber layer defect density on the PV performances of the device.

The absorber layer's morphology has an important effect on the production of photovoltaic solar cells. Generally, photoelectrons are produced in the absorber layer when light is shined upon PSC [47]. Weak film quality may have a major impact on PV output due to carrier trapping and deterioration of carrier transmission properties [48-49]. Since the generation and recombination processes take place within the absorber layer, it's critical to consider how defect densities affect system output in order to achieve full productivity. A decrease in the continuity of doping thresholds and the process of doping in the absorber layer is the primary cause of defect forming, which can influence device performance. As the absorber layer defect is unfavorable for the device performance, it is very much important to study the solar cells behavior with different defect densities. In the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001) layer, only one deep-level donor-like defect was used in this simulation because the production energy of acceptor defects is lower than that of donor defects [50]. The effect of defect densities in the absorber layer on the devices PV performance is depicted in Figure 7. The PV parameters are determined in this simulation by changing the defect densities from 10^{13} cm^{-3} to 10^{17} cm^{-3} . PCE, FF, J_{sc} , and V_{oc} decrease in an additive order as defect density increases, as seen in figures 6(a), 6(b), 6(c), and 6(d), respectively. All the PV parameters are maximum at lower defect density. V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF and PCE falls by a huge margin such as, 0.2-volt, 5.79 mA/cm², 25.65 %, and 19.24 %, respectively, while increasing the defect densities in the range of 10^{13} cm^{-3} to 10^{17} cm^{-3} . These results suggest that, we have to ensure possibly minimum defect density at the absorber layer in order to design the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based efficient solar cells.

Figure 7(a-d): The effect of Defect density of absorber layer on the PV performance parameters of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cells.

3.4. The effect of CuI HTL layer properties (Thickness and Carrier concentration) on the PV performances of the device.

HTM is crucial for the deposition of photogenerated charge carriers from the absorber layer. Because of their low binding energy and long diffusion lengths, the photo-produced excitons in the absorber layer penetrate the interfaces and are separated by the interfaces' SCR field [33]. As a result, holes are transported to the HTL layer, while the HTL layer block the electrons penetration, respectively. The effect of CuI HTL thickness on the device's output was investigated by varying the CuI layer thickness in the range of 0.5 μm to 2.3 μm . As seen in Figure 8(b), as the thickness of the HTL layer increases, J_{sc} increases sharply. It is because of its comparatively higher carrier mobility than the absorber layer. Increasing of HTL layer thickness allow more carrier to enter into it, that facilitates the charge carrier to become more mobile in the layer because of higher carrier mobility. And at the same time, total free carrier increases at the HTL which leads to increase the conductivity and current density. The reduction of photo-generated charge carrier recombination is indicated by an increase in J_{sc} [33]. Figure 8 depicts the response of V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF, and PCE as a function of HTL thickness. Here, the thickness of HTL is varied from 500nm to 2300nm. The V_{oc} and FF are almost insensitive to HTL thickness as shown in figure 8(a) & 8(b). The PCE rises as the thickness of the HTL rises like the same manner of current density. Hence the optimized thickness of HTL is considered as 2.0 μm .

Figure 8(a-d): The effect of Thickness of CuI (HTL) layer on the PV performance parameters of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cells.

The resistance/conductance of the HTM is determined by its doping concentration (N_A), and the doping concentration of CuI layer has a significant impact on the device's efficiency. The doping level of HTM is varied from 10^{16} cm^{-3} to 10^{20} cm^{-3} to understand the impact of HTL carrier concentration on system outputs. Figure 9 shows how the PV parameter changes as HTM doping concentrations increases. Here, the V_{oc} curve shifted upward with higher doping concentration. Increased HTL layer doping improves system efficiency by lowering the recombination rate in the space charge field and after $>10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ carrier concentration PCE start to fall like FF as shown in figure 9(c) and 9(d). However, moderate doping is needed because heavy doping causes the semi-conductive structure of perovskites to shift to metallic, obstructing the carrier transport mechanism [51]. When N_A is set to 10^{19} cm^{-3} , overall PV parameters display the best output.

Figure 9(a-d): The effect of Carrier Concentration of CuI (HTL) layer on the PV performance parameters of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x (0001)-based solar cells.

3.5. The effect of ZnS ETL layer properties (Thickness and Carrier concentration) on the PV performances of the device.

The ETL is responsible for collecting photogenerated electrons from the absorber layer. Because of their low binding energy and long diffusion lengths, the photo-produced excitons in the absorber layer penetrate the interfaces and are separated by the interfaces' SCR field [33]. As a result, electrons are transported to the ETL layer, but the ETL layer block the penetration of holes.

Figure 10(a-d). The effect of Thickness of ZnS (ETL) layer on the PV performance parameters of α -Fe₂O_{3-x}S_x (0001)-based solar cells.

Thickness of the ETL is very crucial parameter to obtain a good performance from the solar cell. Thickness of the ETL should keep as thin as possible than the other layers. The solar cell parameters V_{OC}, J_{SC}, FF, and PCE are

plotted against the thickness of the ETL as represented in Figure 10. As seen in figure 10, the thickness of the ETL varies from 20nm to 50nm. V_{oc} and FF were varied by a very small margin with thickness variation as shown in figure 10(a) and 10(c), respectively. There is a fractional absorption of incident light by the ETMs layer. For this unexpected light absorption, both of bulk and surface recombination arises at the interface, in turns, device experiences series resistance [52]. As a result, J_{sc} and PCE are steadily decreasing with respect to ETL thickness increasement. Therefore, 30nm is considered as the optimized thickness of ETL.

Figure 11(a-d): The effect of Carrier Concentration of ZnS (ETL) layer on the PV performance parameters of α - $Fe_2O_{3-x}S_x$ (0001)-based solar cells.

The electrical activity of every solar cell layer can be determined by the amount doping of a photoactive material in the solar cell architecture, which affects the device's efficiency. Higher ETL carrier concentration increases the device's efficiency by increasing the interface electric field. Figure 11 shows a plot of PV cell parameters as a function of ZnS ETL carrier concentration (N_D). The research was carried out on values ranging from $10^{18} cm^{-3}$ to $10^{21} cm^{-3}$. V_{oc} and J_{sc} shows nearly constant response with increasing N_D as represented in figure 11(a) & 11(b). But figure 11(c) & 11(d) describe that, FF and PCE increases significantly following the increasement of carrier concentration (N_D) of ETL. Here, $10^{21} cm^{-3}$ is considered as the optimized value of N_D for proposed structure.

3.6. The effect of working temperature on the PV performances of the device.

The temperature (T) behavior of solar cells is crucial to understand the performance and the device stability. In most applications, they are exposed to temperatures between 288 and 323 K [53], with even higher temperatures in the desert during the summer [54], as well as in space and concentrator systems [55].

Typically, 300K is selected as the working temperature in this simulation because it is regarded as the room temperature. In fact, the operating temperature varies depending on the location's latitude, altitude, year, and time of day. Furthermore, the operating temperature has an effect on the efficiency of a solar cell. To achieve the actual behavior of α - $Fe_2O_{3-x}S_x$ (0001)-based solar cells, we varied the temperature from 290K to 410K in this context. Figure 12 depicts the variation of PV parameters as a function of solar cell operating temperature, where solar cell output is greatly affected by operating temperature and all the PV parameters goes downward except current density (J_{sc} rises by a very small margin with temperature i.e., nearly constant). Solar cells have shown to do well at room temperature and temperature above room temperature has had a negative impact on overall efficiency. The carrier concentrations, charge carrier stability, resistance, and band gap of the materials will all be significantly influenced at higher temperatures, resulting in changes in PV parameters. Thermal

velocity of hole and electron are directly dependent on the operating temperature which also affected the cell performance as represented in figure 12. This is also well agreed with literature [53].

Figure 12(a-d): The effect of Working Temperature on the PV performance parameters of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cells.

IV. CONCLUSION

$\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)'s suitable optoelectrical characteristics strongly suggest that it may be used in solar cells to replace the CIGS absorbers because of its components scarcity and extremely complex stoichiometric elements based CZTS. In this research work, the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cell with ZnS as ETL and CuI as HTL was studied by SCAPS-1D. The effects of various factors on the PV performance of the cell were discussed. In order to find the best results, work function of back-contact metal, the thickness and carrier concentration of the absorber, HTL and ETL layers, working temperature, and defect density of the absorber layer were all varied. According to the structural study of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_{3-x}\text{S}_x$ (0001)-based solar cell, the thickness of each layer has a substantial influence on cell efficiency. The thickness of absorber, HTL, and ETL were all set to their optimal values of $0.50\mu\text{m}$, $2.0\mu\text{m}$, and $0.03\mu\text{m}$, respectively. According to the simulation data we may conclude that, the proper carrier concentration of all layers (Absorber, HTL, and ETL) improve the PCE. Due to higher recombination rate, a higher carrier concentration in the absorber layer reduces the PCE. The optimum absorber's carrier concentration was set to 1014 cm^{-3} . The optimum carrier concentrations of HTL and ETL were assumed to be 1019 cm^{-3} and 1021 cm^{-3} , respectively. We have discovered that PCE has a good correlation with absorber layer defect density. The device's efficiency improves as the defect density of the absorber layer decreases. The simulation work was done at 300K temperature, which is considered as the optimized condition. The cell performance falls drastically at the higher temperature.

The device structure was studied with three different back-contact metal of Cu(100), Au(111), and Ni(111). Use of Ni as a back-contact shows the best result compared with Cu and Au. After optimizing all the parameters at their respective optimized value, while using Cu as a back-contact metal the power conversion efficiency reaches up to 22.0252% efficiency with a good J_{sc} value ($32.20563422\text{ mA/cm}^2$) and the corresponding FF, VOC are 74.7923%, 0.914387 Volt, respectively at 1015 cm^{-3} absorber defect density. At the time of using Au as a back-contact metal, the power conversion efficiency reaches up to 32.7511% efficiency with a good J_{sc} value

(35.51066mA/cm²) and the corresponding FF, VOC are 78.6965%, 0.861534 volt, respectively at 1015 cm⁻³ absorber defect density. The replacement of other back contact by Ni(111) shows the maximum power conversion efficiency up to 37.2378% at lower absorber defect density and provide 34.1381% efficiency with a good JSC value (46.22611678mA/cm²) and the corresponding FF, VOC are 80.7007%, 0.915114 volt, respectively at 1015 cm⁻³ absorber defect density. These findings explicitly suggest that α -Fe₂O₃-xS_x (0001) may be a viable material for low-cost high performing solar cell chip fabrication.

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Author's Declaration

The authors state that they have no known competing financial interests or personal connections that might have influenced the research presented in this paper.

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